

Jisc

**A review of
transitional
agreements
in the UK:
Appendices**

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Appendix 1: average fully OA and hybrid OA APC and APC percentage increase

Data source: Delta Think

Pricing Year	Average Fully OA APC	Average Fully OA APC % increase	Hybrid OA APC	Average Hybrid OA APC % increase
2022-2023	\$1,962	4.1%	\$3,336	3.8%
2021-2022	\$1,884	4.5%	\$3,215	3.6%
2020-2021	\$1,804	8.1%	\$3,104	5.8%
2019-2020	\$1,668	4.7%	\$2,933	0.7%
2018-2019	\$1,594	0.4%	\$2,913	1.1%
2017-2018	\$1,589	1.2%	\$2,881	0.5%
2016-2017	\$1,570	3.5%	\$2,867	0.0%
2015-2016	\$1,517		\$2,867	

Appendix 2: methodologies

This report is based on an analysis of the current and historical TAs with publishers that had an active TA with Jisc in 2022, listed below.

Figure 38: List of the publishers of transitional agreements that this report is based on

Publisher (of transitional agreement)	Also referred to as	Agreement starting year	Notes
American Chemical Society	ACS	2022	
American Institute of Physics Publishing LLC	AIP	2021	
American Physiological Society	APS	2021	
American Psychological Association	APA	2022	Excluded from all analyses, as data not available when research was conducted
Association for Computing Machinery, Inc.	ACM	2020	
Bentham Science Publishers Ltd. (FZE)	Bentham	2022	
Bioscientifica Limited	Bioscientifica	2021	
BMJ Publishing Group Limited	BMJ	2021	
Cambridge University Press (Holdings) Limited	CUP	2021	
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press	CSHLP	2021	Excluded from analysis of cost offsetting, as no article-level data provided by publisher in 2022
Elsevier B.V.	Elsevier	2022	
European Respiratory Society	ERS	2020	
Future Science Limited	Future Science	2021	
Georg Thieme Verlag KG	Thieme	2020	
IOP Publishing Limited	IOP	2020	
IWA Publishing Limited	IWAP	2020	
John Benjamins Uitgeverij BV	John Benjamins	2022	
Koninklijke Brill NV	Brill	2021	
Microbiology Society		2020	
National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America	NAS	2021	

Publisher (of transitional agreement)	Also referred to as	Agreement starting year	Notes
Optical Society of America, Incorporated (The)	Optica	2022	Excluded from analysis of cost offsetting, as no article-level data collected for publisher
Oxford University Press	OUP	2021	
Portland Press Limited	Portland Press	2020	
Radiological Society of North America	RSNA	2021	Excluded from analysis of cost avoidance, as unable to separate 'read' and 'publish' fees
Royal College of General Practitioners	RCGP	2021	
Royal Irish Academy	RIA	2021	Excluded from analysis of cost avoidance, as unable to separate 'read' and 'publish' fees
Royal Society		2021	
Royal Society of Chemistry	RSC	2020	
S. Karger AG	Karger	2021	
SAGE Publications Limited	Sage	2020	
Springer Nature (UK) Limited	Springer Nature	2016	Excluded from cost analysis, as TAs preceded the 2022 TA to before 2018
Taylor & Francis Group Limited	Taylor & Francis, T&F	2019	Excluded from analysis of cost avoidance, as unable to separate 'read' and 'publish' fees
The Company of Biologists Ltd	Company of Biologists, CoB	2020	
The Geological Society of London	GSL	2021	
The Rockefeller University	Rockefeller	2020	
University of Bristol	BUP	2022	Excluded from analysis of cost offsetting, as no article-level data provided by publisher
Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co. KG	De Gruyter	2021	
Wiley Subscription Services Inc	Wiley	2020	
Wolters Kluwer Health (Medical Research) Ltd	Wolters Kluwer	2022	

Prevalence of OA in global and UK literature

Scope

Publishers: refer to [figure 38](#). 38 publishers were included (APA was excluded as data was not available when this research was conducted).

Transitional agreements: Jisc-negotiated TAs that were in existence prior to (and including) 2022, with the publishers in scope. Note, this excludes historical TAs with publishers that no longer have a current TA. Specific agreement names are listed in the table below.

Journals: those journals that were included in a title list associated with the TAs in scope. From Knowledge Base+ [KB+], those title lists are identified in [figure 39](#). Note that five journals were removed from the dataset as they ceased publication before 2015 or contained conference proceedings exclusively.

Figure 39: Knowledge Base+ [KB+] title lists of journals associated with a publisher's transitional agreement that were used to identify the scope of the analysis in section 2.

Publisher	Agreement name	KB+ title list
American Chemical Society	American Chemical Society Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2024	American Chemical Society_Jisc Collections_American Chemical Society Read & Publish Agreement 2022-2024 (Publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
American Institute of Physics Publishing LLC	American Institute of Physics Read and Publish agreement 2021-23	American Institute of Physics_Jisc Collections_Transitional Journals Agreement 2021-23 (Publishing list) as at 2022-07-28
American Physiological Society	American Physiological Society Read, Publish & Join Agreement 2021-22	American Physiological Society_Jisc Collections_American Physiological Society Journals _Read Publish & Join_ Agreement_2021-2022 (Publishing list) as at 2022-07-28
Association for Computing Machinery, Inc.	ACM Open Journals Publish and Read Agreement 2020-2022	Association for Computing Machinery_Jisc Collections_ACM Open 2020-2022 (publishing list) as at 2022-08-17
Bentham Science Publishers Ltd. (FZE)	Bentham Science Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2023	Bentham Science_Jisc Collections_Bentham Science Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2023 (Publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
Bioscientifica Limited	Bioscientifica Read and Publish Agreement 2021-2022	Bioscientifica_Jisc Collections_Bioscientifica Journals _Read & Publish_ Transitional Agreement 2021-2022 (pilot) (Publishing List) as at 2022-07-28

Publisher	Agreement name	KB+ title list
BMJ Publishing Group Limited	BMJ publish and read agreement 2022	British Medical Journal_Jisc Collections_BMJ Publish and Read Agreement 2022_ Standard Collection and Gold Titles Addition (publishing list) as at 2022-12-31
		British Medical Journal_Jisc Collections_BMJ Publish and Read Agreement 2022_Standard Collection (publishing list) as at 2022-12-31
		British Medical Journal_Jisc Collections_BMJ Publish and Read Agreement 2022_Standard Collection and Hybrid Journals Addition (publishing list) as at 2022-12-31
	BMJ Publish and Read Agreement 2021 Pilot	British Medical Journal_Jisc Collections_BMJ Publish and Read Pilot Agreement 2021 (publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
Koninklijke Brill NV	Brill Journals Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2022	Brill_Jisc Collections_Brill Journals Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2022 (Publishing list) as at 2022-08-17
		Brill_SHEDL_Brill Journals Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2022 (Publishing list) as at 2022-08-17
University of Bristol	BUP Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2023	Bristol University Press_Jisc Collections_BUP Journals Collection Read and Publish 2022-2023 (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
Cambridge University Press (Holdings) Limited	CUP Read and Publish Agreement 2021-24	Cambridge University Press_Jisc Collections_Cambridge University Press Read and Publish Agreement 2021-2024 (Publishing list) as at 2022-07-28
		Cambridge University Press_Jisc Collections_Cambridge University Press Read and Publish Agreement 2021-2024- HE in FE (Publishing list) as at 2022-08-22
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press	CSHLP Read and Publish agreement 2021-2022	Jisc Collections_Cold Spring Harbor Journals Read & Publish Transitional Agreement 2021-2022 (Publishing List) as at 2022-07-28
The Company of Biologists Ltd	Company of Biologists Jisc Collections Transitional Agreement 2022-2024	Company of Biologists_Jisc Collections_Transitional Agreement 2022-2024_3 Journals Publish Fee (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
		Company of Biologists_Jisc Collections_Transitional Agreement 2022-2024_5 Journals Publish Fee (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
	The Company of Biologists 'Read & Publish' 1 year Agreement 2021	Company of Biologists_Jisc Collections_The Company of Biologists _Read & Publish_ 1 year Agreement 2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
	Company of Biologists 'Read & Publish' Transitional Agreement 2020-21 (Pilot)	Company of Biologists_Jisc Collections__Read & Publish_ Transitional Agreement (Pilot) 2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31

Publisher	Agreement name	KB+ title list
Elsevier B.V.	Elsevier Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2024	<p>Elsevier_Jisc Collections_Elsevier Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2024 (Fully Gold titles) as at 2023-03-09</p> <p>Elsevier_Jisc Collections_Elsevier Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2024 (Publishing list) as at 2023-03-09</p> <p>Elsevier_Jisc Collections_Elsevier Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2024_The Lancet as at 2023-03-09</p>
European Respiratory Society	European Respiratory Society Read & Publish Agreement 2022-2023	<p>European Respiratory Society_Jisc Collections_European Respiratory Society Read & Publish 2022-2023_Option 2_ European Respiratory Journal, ERJ Open Research & European Respiratory Review (Publishing List)</p> <p>European Respiratory Society_Jisc Collections_European Respiratory Society Read & Publish 2022-2023_Option 1_ European Respiratory Journal Only (Publishing list) as at 2023-03-09</p>
	European Respiratory Society Jisc Collections 1 year Agreement 2021	European Respiratory Society_Jisc Collections_European Respiratory Journal Read and Publish One Year Agreement 2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
	European Respiratory Journal 'Read & Publish' Transitional Agreement 2020-2021 (Pilot)	European Respiratory Society_Jisc Collections_European Respiratory Journal _Read & Publish_ Transitional Agreement (Pilot) 2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
Future Science Limited	Future Science Group Read and Publish agreement 2021-2022	Future Science Group_Jisc Collections__Read & Publish_ Transitional Agreement 2021-2022 (Reading and Publishing List) as at 2022-08-02
The Geological Society of London	Geological Society Lyell Collection Read & Publish Agreement 2022 & Option on 2023	Geological Society_Jisc Collections_Geological Society Lyell Collection Read & Publish Agreement 2022-2023(Publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
	Geological Society Jisc Transitional Agreement 2021	Geological Society_Jisc Collections_Geological Society Lyell Collection Read & Publish Agreement 2021(Publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
IOP Publishing Limited	IOP Publishing Read and Publish agreement 2020-2023	<p>Institute of Physics_Jisc Collections_IOP Publishing Read & Publish agreement 2020-2023 (partner publishing list) as at 2022-08-02</p> <p>Institute of Physics_Jisc Collections_IOP Publishing Read & Publish agreement 2020-2023 (publishing list) as at 2022-08-02</p> <p>Institute of Physics_Jisc Collections_IOP Publishing Read & Publish agreement 2020-2023_ECS Plus Upgrade (publishing list) as at 2022-08-02</p>

Publisher	Agreement name	KB+ title list
IWA Publishing Limited	IWA Publishing (IWAP) Journals Read & Publish Agreement 2022-2024	IWA Publishing (IWAP)_Jisc Collections_IWAP Journals Read and Publish 2022-2024 (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
	IWA Publishing Jisc Collections 1 Year Agreement 2021	IWA Publishing (IWAP)_Jisc Collections_Read & Publish 1 Year Agreement 2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
	IWA Publishing (IWAP) Journals 'Read & Publish' Transitional Agreement 2020-21 (Pilot)	IWA Publishing (IWAP)_Jisc Collections__Read & Publish_ Transitional Agreement (Pilot) 2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
John Benjamins Uitgeverij B.V.	John Benjamins Read and Publish agreement 2022-2024	John Benjamins Publishing_Jisc Collections_John Benjamins Read and Publish 2022-2024 (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
S. Karger AG	Karger Journals Read and Publish SMP Agreement 2021-2023	Karger_Jisc Collections_Karger Journals Read and Publish SMP Agreement 2021-2023 (publishing list) as at 2022-08-02
Microbiology Society	Microbiology Society Journals Portfolio "Publish & Read" 1 year Agreement 2022	Microbiology Society_Jisc Collections_Microbiology Society Journals _Publish & Read_ 1 year Agreement 2022 (publishing list) as at 2022-12-31
	Microbiology Society Jisc Collections 1 year Agreement 2021 (Pilot)	Microbiology Society_Jisc Collections_Microbiology Society Journals Portfolio _Publish & Read_ 1 Year Agreement 2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
	Microbiology Society Journals Portfolio 'Publish & Read' Transitional Agreement 2020-2021 (Pilot)	Microbiology Society_Jisc Collections_Microbiology Society Journals Portfolio _Publish & Read_ Transitional Agreement_2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America	PNAS Publish and Read agreement 2021-23	National Academy of Sciences_Jisc Collections_PNAS Publish & Read 2021-2023 Agreement (Publishing and reading list) as at 2022-08-03
Optical Society of America, Incorporated (The) (Optica)	Optica Publishing Group Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 2022-24	Optica Publishing Group_Jisc Collections_Optica Publishing Group Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 2022-2024 (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
Oxford University Press	OUP Full Collection Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2023	Oxford University Press_Jisc Collections_OUP Full Collection Read & Publish Agreement 2021 (Publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
		Oxford University Press_SHEDL_OUP Full Collection Read & Publish Agreement 2021 (Publishing list) as at 2021-12-31

Publisher	Agreement name	KB+ title list
Portland Press Limited	Portland Press all-inclusive Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 2022	Portland Press_Jisc Collections_Portland Press All-Inclusive Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 2022 (publishing list) as at 2022-12-31
	Portland Press Jisc Collections 1 Year agreement 2021 (Pilot)	Portland Press_Jisc Collections_ Portland Press All-Inclusive Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 1 Year_2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
	Portland Press All-Inclusive Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 2020-2021 (pilot)	Portland Press_Jisc Collections Portland Press _All-Inclusive Read and Publish Transitional Agreement(Pilot)_2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
Radiological Society of North America	RSNA Journals Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2022	Radiological Society of North America_Jisc Collections_RSNA Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2022 (Publishing list) as at 2022-08-03
The Rockefeller University	Rockefeller University Press 2 year Transitional Agreement 2022-2023	Rockefeller University Press_Jisc Collections_Transitional Agreement 2022-2023 (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
	Rockefeller University Press Read & Publish 1 year Agreement 2021	Jisc Collections_Rockefeller University Press Read and Publish One Year Agreement 2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2022-02-28
	Rockefeller University Press Transitional 'Read and Publish' 2020-22 (Pilot)	Rockefeller University Press_Jisc Collections_'Read and Publish' Transitional Agreement (Pilot) 2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2022-02-28
Royal College of General Practitioners	RCGP Journals: Read and Publish Agreement 2021-2022	Royal College of General Practitioners _Jisc Collections_RCGP Journals _Read & Publish_ Transitional Agreement 2021-2022 (pilot) (Reading and Publishing List) as at 2022-08-03
		Royal College of General Practitioners_Jisc Collections_RCGP Journals _Read & Publish_ Transitional Agreement 2021-2022 (pilot) (Publishing List) as at 2022-08-22
Royal Irish Academy	Royal Irish Academy Journals Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2022	Royal Irish Academy_Jisc Collections_Jisc RIA Journals Read & Publish Agreement 2021-2022 (publishing list) as at 2022-08-03
Royal Society	Royal Society Journals Read & Publish Transitional Agreement 2022	Royal Society Publishing_Jisc Collections_Royal Society Journals Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 2022 (publishing List) as at 2022-12-31
	Royal Society Jisc Transitional Agreement 2021	Royal Society Publishing_Jisc Collections_Royal Society Journals Read and Publish Transitional Agreement 2021 (Publishing List) as at 2021-12-31

Publisher	Agreement name	KB+ title list
Royal Society of Chemistry	Royal Society of Chemistry Read and Publish Agreement 2022-2024	Royal Society of Chemistry_Jisc Collections_Royal Society of Chemistry Read and Publish 2022-2024 (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09 Royal Society of Chemistry_Jisc Collections_Royal Society of Chemistry Read and Publish 2022-2024_(Discounted Gold OA) as at 2023-03-09
	Royal Society of Chemistry 2020-2021 Agreement Read and Publish	Royal Society of Chemistry_Jisc Collections_Journals Agreement 2020-21, Option 4_ upgrade to unlimited Open Access publishing as at 2021-12-31 Royal Society of Chemistry_Jisc Collections_Royal Society of Chemistry Read and Publish Journals Agreement 2020-2021(Publishing List) as at 2021-12-31
Sage	SAGE Journals Read and Publish agreement 2020-22	Sage_Jisc Collections_SAGE Journals Read & Publish 2020-2022 Agreement (Publishing List_uncapped) as at 2022-08-03 Sage_SHEDL_SAGE Journals Read & Publish 2020-2022 Agreement (Publishing List_uncapped) as at 2022-08-22 SAGE_WHEEL_WHEEL SAGE Journals Collection 2020-22 Agreement 2020-2022 as at 2022-08-22
Springer Nature (UK) Limited	SpringerCompact Journals Agreement 2016-2018	Springer_Jisc Collections_Compact_2016-2018 as at 2018-12-31
	SpringerCompact Journals Agreement 2019-2021	Springer_Jisc Collections_SpringerCompact Journals Agreement 2019-2021 (publishing list) as at 2021-12-31 Springer_SHEDL_Compact_2019-2021 as at 2021-12-31
	SpringerCompact Journals Agreement 2021-2022	Springer_Jisc Collections_SpringerCompact Journals Agreement 2021-2022 - Existing Subscribers Only(Publishing List) as at 2022-08-17
Taylor & Francis Group Limited	Taylor & Francis Read and Publish agreement 2021-23	Taylor & Francis_Jisc Collections_Transformative Agreement 2021-2023 (Publishing list - all titles) as at 2022-08-17

Publisher	Agreement name	KB+ title list
Georg Thieme Verlag KG	Thieme transitional OA agreement 2022-23	Georg Thieme Verlag_Jisc Collections_Thieme 2022-2023 Journals Transitional OA Agreement (SMP)_Chemistry Collection (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
		Georg Thieme Verlag_Jisc Collections_Thieme 2022-2023 Journals Transitional OA Agreement (SMP)_Medical Collection (publishing list) as at 2023-03-09
	Thieme Journals SMP Read and Publish Agreement 2020 to 2021	Georg Thieme Verlag_Jisc Collections_Transitional Open Access Chemistry Collection 2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
		Georg Thieme Verlag_Jisc Collections_Transitional Open Access Medical Collection 2020-2021 (reading and publishing list) as at 2021-12-31
Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co. KG	De Gruyter Read & Publish agreement 2021-23	De Gruyter_Jisc Collections_De Gruyter Journal and Open Access Transformational Agreement 2021-2023_Complete Package (Reading and publishing List) as at 2022-07-28
		Walter De Gruyter_Jisc Collections_De Gruyter Journal and Open Access Transformational Agreement 2021-2023_HSS English Package (Reading and publishing list) as at 2022-08-22
		Walter De Gruyter_Jisc Collections_De Gruyter Journal and Open Access Transformational Agreement 2021-2023_STM Package (Reading and publishing list) as at 2022-08-22
Wiley Subscription Services Inc	Wiley Read and Publish agreement 2020-2023	Wiley_Jisc Collections_Wiley Jisc Read and Publish Open Access Agreement 2020-2023 (publishing list) as at 2022-08-17
		Wiley_Jisc Collections_Wiley Jisc Read and Publish Open Access Agreement 2020-2023_Upgrade 2021(publishing list) as at 2022-08-17
		Wiley_WHEEL_Wiley Jisc Read and Publish Open Access Agreement 2020-2023 (publishing list) as at 2022-08-17
		Wiley_WHEEL_Wiley Jisc Read and Publish Open Access Agreement 2020-2023_Upgrade 2021(publishing list) as at 2022-08-17
Wolters Kluwer Health (Medical Research) Ltd	Wolters Kluwer Read and Publish Pilot 2022-2024	Wolters Kluwer_Jisc Collections_Wolters Kluwer Transitional OA Agreement (Pilot 2022 to 2024) 2022-2024 (Publishing List) as at 2023-03-09

Years: article- and journal-level data was obtained for 2018 to 2022 inclusive. This timespan was chosen as it provides the best balance of practicality in retrieving data with robustness of analysis. Some high-level figures (from ESAC Transformative Agreement Registry and Dimensions web app) show a longer time period (ie, from as early as 2014).

Data sources

Data about scholarly publications is fragmented across multiple sources. To understand patterns in OA uptake within the relevant title lists, we combined data from several sources and analysed it. Sources cover a mix of journal-level and article-level metadata, within the scope defined above unless otherwise specified.

1. KB+: for title lists of journals associated with TAs
2. Dimensions Analytics API: for article-level metadata for articles published in journals and years in scope
3. Dimensions web app: for summary number of articles per publisher per year (for 2014 to 2022), globally as well as with research org location = United Kingdom, for each OA type. Retrieved April 2023
4. Delta Think: for a list of journals that (were likely to have) flipped to Gold status, since 2015
5. JCT API: for journal-level compliance of journals in scope, limited to compliance statuses of Gold or Hybrid
6. DOAJ Change Log¹ (as of 7 Sept 2023): for journal-level Gold status over time
7. Article-level metadata (provided by publishers to Jisc): for summary number of articles published under Jisc-negotiated TA (in the UK) per publisher, per year (from 2018 on, when available)
8. ESAC Transformative Agreement Registry: for figures on global transitional agreements and research outputs under global TAs by publisher. Additional publishers from scope included for analysis of global TA trends. Retrieved March 2023
9. Licence subscriptions manager: for a list of organisations subscribing to the TAs in scope. Limited to orders dated in the last ten years
10. Unpaywall API: for a list of articles that also had a copy in a repository (and therefore were also Green). Queries limited to Gold and Hybrid articles (as only Gold and Hybrid articles would mask an article with a Green copy). Any article with an oa_locations_#_host_type equal to 'repository' was defined as having a Green copy
11. Internal reports: for other fields characterising research organisations

Definitions

Authorship

- UK publication: countries of research organisations of all affiliated authors includes United Kingdom
- Corresponding author: the corresponding author as identified by Dimensions, or where not available, the first listed author
- UK corresponding author publication: for UK publications, the corresponding author is affiliated with a research organisation in the United Kingdom (the affiliated organisation is in the 'country' 'United Kingdom', or the raw affiliation includes 'United Kingdom' or 'UK')
- UK CA affiliated organisation: the first organisation affiliated with the UK corresponding author that is located in the United Kingdom (based on the first affiliated organisation with 'country' 'United Kingdom', or where not available, the raw affiliation includes 'United Kingdom' or 'UK')
- UK CA Jisc member publication: the UK CA affiliated organisation has a JOID (and therefore is a Jisc member)

Open Access status

The article-level data included a single OA status, based on Unpaywall definitions (Priem, 2021², emphasis in original):

“Green articles are published in toll-access journals, but archived in an OA archive, or ‘repository’. These repositories may be discipline-specific (like ArXiv) or institutional repositories operated by universities or other institutions. Green articles may be published versions or preprints, and can have any license or no license.

Bronze articles are free to read on the publisher’s website, without a license that grants any other rights. There may be a delay between publication and availability to read, and often articles can be removed unilaterally by the publisher.

Hybrid articles are free to read at the time of publication, with an open license. These are usually published in exchange for an article processing charge, or APC.

Gold articles have all the same characteristics as Hybrid articles, but are published in all-Open Access journals, which are in turn called ‘Gold journals’, or just ‘OA journals’.

Closed articles are a fifth OA status assigned by Unpaywall, where none of the above OA categories apply.”

For the purposes of this report we combined or renamed the Unpaywall OA categories for clarity, as follows:

- ‘**Closed**’ refers to Closed and Bronze articles as defined above, unless otherwise specified, ie, as ‘Closed (only)’
- ‘**Open**’ refers to Gold and Hybrid articles as defined above
- ‘**Green-only**’ refers to Green articles as defined above, whereas ‘Green’ articles includes all articles with a copy in a repository (ie, including Gold and Hybrid articles)

- Any references to Bronze, Hybrid, or Gold use the definitions outlined by Unpaywall above
- ‘**Gold and Green**’ refers to Gold articles (as defined above) that also have a copy in a repository
- ‘**Hybrid and Green**’ refers to Hybrid articles (as defined above) that also have a copy in a repository

Journal compliance status

- Fully OA title: ‘fully OA’ compliance route; listed in DOAJ Directory of Open Access Journals
- Flipped journal: a journal is deemed ‘flipped’ if it is fully OA in the year, but was not fully OA previously
- Certainty of flip:
 - Likely: price list data for both years (so status can confirm from the publisher’s price lists before and after the flip)
 - Maybe: price list data for one year or the other (but not both)
 - Possible: no price list data (so must estimate only from the numbers of papers)

Method

Overall, our methodology involved linking sources using best available identifiers (typically International Standard Serial Numbers [ISSNs]) so articles could be categorised or identified by journal, journal type, a journal’s presence in a relevant TA, publisher, article OA status and author/s’ location (country). The article-level data were then aggregated to extract patterns relevant to the analysis.

A list of TAs was retrieved from the Jisc website. Historical agreements were also sought (for publishers with active TAs on the Jisc website) by searching for the publishers with current TAs on KB+. The combined list of TAs was then limited to TAs that had been active during or before 2022, had associated journal title lists and were held on LSM. The related KB+ lists and LSM products were identified.

The journals in all of the relevant KB+ lists from the scope were used as the basis for the following work. In cases where a journal was listed by more than one publisher in KB+ lists, the first publisher of the journal was used for each year before the second publisher of the journal included the journal in their TA list. Where a journal was listed by more than one publisher in KB+ lists in the same year, the publisher associated with relevant Dimensions records was used.

The journal-level metadata was enhanced (based on a match between any of the available ISSNs), with:

1. Classification as a flipped journal, with likelihood and year of flip, based on a list of flipped journals, and
2. Compliance status information from the Journal Checker Tool API

The journal-level metadata from KB+ was enhanced with classification as a flipped journal, going back to 2015.

To determine whether a journal has flipped to OA, where available, a journal's access type was first collated from publishers' websites and price lists where available or, if listed, from the DOAJ, the Bielefeld Gold ISSNs study, the OpenAPC study and ROAD³. These lists cover around 45% of the ~120,000 journals in the OpenAlex data set, covering around 70% of the papers published by journals listed in OpenAlex.

Where not available, journal access types are inferred from patterns in the Unpaywall OA status of papers published each year. For example, where a journal only publishes Gold papers according to Unpaywall, it is deemed fully OA in a given year. Similarly for Hybrid papers. Delta Think also tries to correct for noise (anomalies) in the data. Eg, if a journal seems to be Hybrid most years, but fully OA for just one year, then it's likely to be Hybrid, and the automated tools were unable to pick up licences correctly in the anomalous year.

A journal is deemed 'flipped' if it is fully OA in a given year, but was not fully OA previously.

Due to the varying reliability of data, each flip was rated with a 'likelihood', which is defined from most to least certain as likely, maybe, or possible (see [definitions](#)). Because of the variability of data, these lists should be taken as estimates.

Journal-level data was further enhanced with historical compliance status as a fully OA journal based on results from the Journal Checker Tool (JCT) API⁴ and the DOAJ list of journals added and removed⁵. The Journal Checker Tool API was used to specifically identify Gold journals ('fully OA' according to the JCT output). As the JCT API was run in 2023, the DOAJ Change Log was used to logically determine whether journals were Gold OA in years prior to 2023, going back to 2018. Titles deduced as Gold OA in a given year in this way are labelled in the report as 'fully OA titles'.

Article-level data was retrieved from the Dimensions Analytics API between August 2022 and March 2023⁶, for all of the journal ISSNs in scope for the years 2018 to 2022.⁷ (Note: the listed publisher in the final dataset was generally sourced from the relevant KB+ lists, rather than the Dimensions Analytics API, to ensure that the articles counted match with the publishers of their corresponding title lists).

We cleaned the article-level data and added classification fields, including classification as a UK publication, and as a publication with a UK corresponding author (CA). Where there was a UK CA, the first UK-affiliated organisation was identified. Records with a UK-affiliated organisation were then compared to a list of Jisc members for classification as a UK CA Jisc member publication. This report therefore refers to authorship according to the definitions listed above.

To identify articles that may have had multiple OA statuses, Gold and Hybrid articles as defined above were further enhanced with a secondary OA status, where the article also had a copy in a repository, from the Unpaywall API. Where there was a repository copy, we assigned a secondary OA status (eg, 'Gold and Green' or 'Hybrid and Green'). Note that these categories are included in the 'Open' group and they exclude Green-only articles.

We combined article-level publication data with subscription data from Jisc's licence subscriptions manager (LSM), based on the UK organisation affiliated with the CA and the article's publisher and the year (where the article was published in a period when the relevant TA was active). The LSM subscription data was built from combining several reports on LSM products and subscriptions, and enhanced with additional classifications and identifiers for the subscribing organisations, including Jisc bands. The subscription dataset was then limited to subscriptions to products

associated with TAs. This allowed later identification of which organisations affiliated with the CA were subscribed to the relevant TA during the year the article was published.

The journal-level data was joined with the article-level data based on ISSN and year.

Then, we created summaries of article- and journal-level figures in several formats for further analysis and reporting, including article counts:

- Per journal, per year
- Per journal, per year, for UK or not UK publications, and for each article Open Access status
- Per UK CA affiliated organisation, per publisher, per year

Calculations were added determining the rate of increase in OA content year-on-year for each journal.

Publisher-level data was the result of summarised results from the above process, for each publisher and each year of publication, which we enhanced with:

- The number of research outputs published under TAs (from publisher article-level metadata (ALM) provided to Jisc (where available))
- The number of research outputs published each year, globally and from the UK (from the Dimensions web app, retrieved October 2023)
- The number of research outputs published under TAs globally (from ESAC Transformative Agreement Registry⁸), and
- The number of TAs globally (from ESAC Transformative Agreement Registry)

These datasets were matched on the publisher and year after cleaning.

We added a calculation of the proportions of global articles published covered by global TA agreements, for each publisher. The percentage of the publisher's whole portfolio of articles in a given year (from Dimensions summary data) that were published under global TAs (from ESAC) was calculated for 2018 to 2022.

In addition, worldwide and nationwide figures were obtained from the Dimensions web app, summarising the number of articles by year and OA status (beyond the scope of publishers listed in [figure 38](#)). To estimate the number of Gold articles that were Gold and Green or Gold-only, and likewise the number of Hybrid articles that were Hybrid and Green or Hybrid-only across all publishers, the proportion of each OA category at the article level (as described above for the relevant publishers with Jisc TAs) was used as the basis of an estimation of the split of the broader OA category (eg, 'Gold') into the more specific subcategories (eg, 'Gold and Green'). We imputed the proportions for 2014 to 2017 based on the average annual change in the proportion of the Gold and Hybrid subcategories between 2018 and 2022.

Similarly, the ESAC Transformative Agreement Registry was used as a source for figures on global TAs and research outputs under global TAs beyond those publishers included in the scope of the main analysis.

Limitations

Data sources about research output are distinct in their coverage, method, completeness and accuracy. Many rely on organisations depositing data, the timing, consistency and accuracy of which varies. The raw data behind any analysis of research output is therefore subject to errors and the resulting analyses will be approximate.

Unpaywall's listing of an OA status is sometimes inconsistent, as it may show a mix of Gold and Hybrid articles in the same journal in the same year. This technically should not occur, as the article's OA status should be determined by the journal's status: articles in a fully OA journal should all be Gold. In conversation with Delta Think, Unpaywall has looked into this anomaly and found that the effects of this error are small, perhaps shifting OA proportions by 1% or 2%, with little effect on underlying trends, especially over the relatively short timeframes covered here.

In this analysis the status of each title as fully OA is applied per year, based on whether the title was in the DOAJ at any point in the year. Thus, even where journals are identified as fully OA they may not have been fully OA for the entire year. Articles within fully OA titles that are not classified as Gold OA articles by Unpaywall may be 1) incorrectly classified, resulting in an underestimation of the proportion of Gold and Open articles, or 2)

correctly classified as not Gold OA articles, which may have been published outside the dates when a title was fully OA.

Application of the 'Gold and Green' and 'Hybrid and Green' OA statuses from the article-level data to the global and UK summary figures may not be representative of the real global and UK 'masking' of Green articles, as the article-level data is focused on the subset of journals and publishers in TAs. Similarly, imputation of the 'and Green' OA rates before 2018 from the 2018 to 2022 data may not be representative, as the trend may not be linear as assumed by the model. These global and UK figures for Gold and Green and Hybrid and Green should therefore be treated as estimates only, for the purposes of bringing light to articles that were already OA by virtue of being in a repository (Green) but appeared to be OA only by virtue of being put through a TA or paying an APC (Gold or Hybrid). In this way, we aim to avoid under-reporting Green OA articles when shadowed by other OA statuses.

Furthermore, the OA status of each article is determined at the point of retrieving the data from Dimensions, so articles may have been under embargo at the time of publication, but now show as Green-only after the embargo period has passed. Conversely, more recent articles may show as 'Closed' if they are under embargo, but be eligible for Green OA status in the future. Overall, this makes determining and interpreting the figures related to Green OA articles difficult. Green OA articles may be exaggerated in earlier years of the analysis and under-reported in later years due to the embargo delay. As the proportion of Green articles is likely to increase for articles younger than 2020, any trends noted for the change in Green articles are probably conservative.

The timing of data extraction from Dimensions also affects data quality in terms of publication dates: articles may be published online ahead of print (or ahead of completed journal issues). So, in the early part of each calendar year, publication dates of articles published near the end of the previous year may move into the new year as print versions of journals come out. This can have a profound effect on OA proportions⁹. As we accessed data from Dimensions in March 2023 this might have a small effect on data for 2022, potentially inflating apparent 2021 OA uptake and reducing apparent 2022 OA uptake.

The count of articles published is based on those articles reported in Dimensions, which does not cover all publications. Figures between Dimensions and publisher-reported ALM may differ and, in rare instances, Dimensions may report fewer articles than are reported in publisher-reported ALM. In this case, it should be understood that at least as many articles were published as is reported in the publisher ALM. What's more, at an article-level, approximately one-third of articles in the publisher-reported ALM were not listed in the Dimensions ALM (by DOI). As the analyses are based on the summary count from the publisher-provided ALM, and thereby include articles that are not present in Dimensions ALM dataset, the proportion of articles under a TA may be overestimated.

For example, the comparatively high figures for the Royal Irish Academy should be heavily caveated with limitations on the number of global articles returned (from Dimensions), likely under-reporting their articles published.

The CA analysis identifies the CA where it is known and estimates it where one is not identified by Dimensions. Similarly, the organisation selected from the CA's affiliations is the first UK organisation, but this may not be the institution the author was actually affiliated with at the time of publication and/or the organisation that the article was published under. Due to the complexity of the raw affiliation data, UK organisations remained unidentified for 18 records with a UK CA, and many organisations may be identified multiple times but in slightly different ways. Figures for UK CA and publications by UK CA institutions should therefore be considered as estimates only.

The reliability of the Dimensions filter for 'article' type is uncertain. As Dimensions uses just six, broad categories of publication types, the article category will probably include content other than research or review articles, such as op-ed or errata.

The title lists from KB+ were not consistently available for every year of the TAs. Where only one title list was available, we used it for the duration of the agreement. These lists were not always completely accurate for each year, and in some cases included journals that had ceased publication or were not publishing research articles. Where known, we removed these journals but not all journals included in the lists would have been appropriate to the scope of this analysis.

This analysis assumes that an organisation subscribing to a particular TA had the ability to publish OA in every title in that TA. However, depending on the terms and product options available for each TA, subscribing organisations may not have had OA publishing access to all TA titles in an agreement. This means that the number of articles or organisations counted as published with a subscription to the TA may be overestimated, and conversely that the number of articles or organisations counted as published outside of a subscription may be underestimated.

Prevalence of OA by subject and publisher share

For subject and publisher share analyses using Delta Think data, the sample and method are different (refer to [figure 12](#), [figure 13](#), [figure 20](#), [figure 22](#) and [figure 23](#)). Delta Think focused on an estimate of the addressable market, defined as journals for which publishers are likely to charge fees to read or publish. The long tail of community journals is important but unlikely to incur fees, or be part of TAs (or other spend on publishing). The July 2021 OpenAlex data snapshot was used as a baseline and we inferred a list of journals using ISSN-Ls. A subset of 'certified' journals was taken, defined as those that have one of: The Norwegian Register for Scientific Journals, Series and Publishers¹⁰ Level 1 or 2 status, DOAJ Seal¹¹, or have a SNIP¹². Journals were also matched to information from publishers' OA pricelists using ISSNs to infer their type (fully OA, Hybrid, or no OA option), and OA article counts reclassified to match journal type if needed. Journals are also classified according to the Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC) taxonomy but expanded based on Delta Think's own work on classifying health sciences journals. At the time of writing, Delta Think had not produced its market data for 2022, so extrapolated 2018-2021 figures using linear regression for each category total (subject field or publisher for each access type).

Limitations

Refer to limitations under '[Prevalence of OA in global and UK literature](#)'.

International comparison

We approached selected international consortia and related organisations¹³ to invite them to collaborate and undertake an analysis for their country's TAs, comparing levels of OA in their respective TA titles. Of the 21 organisations we contacted six responded, and two were able to participate in the exercise for inclusion in this report: Universiteitsbibliotheken en Nationale Bibliotheek (UKB) in the Netherlands and Sikt, the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research.

Limitations

We recommend, therefore, that inferences drawn from the analysis should be limited given the low number of results received from international consortia/organisations, which may represent a sampling bias. For example, it may be that organisations able to contribute to this analysis were those with more readily available and cleaned datasets, and/or those with more resources available to support data requests and OA initiatives more broadly.

Cost analysis

We used the TAs with the publishers identified in [figure 38](#) as a basis for analysing actual cost savings achieved through the TAs, modelling cost avoidance and the proportion of reading costs offset by publishing costs, with the exception of Springer Nature (see note below). Agreement metadata was enhanced with data from LSM to include subscriptions to these agreements and expenditures on the read and publish elements of the agreement. Data was also included on subscribers' expenditure with the publisher in the year preceding the TA (on read-only subscriptions and individual APC payments [as reported to Jisc by the publisher])¹⁴.

Expenditure on APCs in the year prior to the TA was not known for all publishers. Estimated values of pre-TA APC expenditure were imputed for publishers without known APC expenditure pre-TA. See [figure 40](#) for details of how we imputed the pre-TA APC expenditure.

Figure 40: list of publishers with unknown pre-TA APC expenditure and imputed estimates.

Publisher	Pre-TA Year	Estimated pre-TA APC expenditure	Calculated as	Notes
American Institute of Physics	2020	£80,428.43	Known spend of participating organisations on Hybrid OA in 2018 (\$103,400) converted to GBP at 2018 currency exchange rate (0.757124) ¹⁵ , and multiplied for inflation between 2018 and 2020 (1.0274) ¹⁶ .	
Association for Computing Machinery	2021	£998.37	Number of 2021 OA articles published by organisations subscribing in 2022 (1), multiplied by average Hybrid APC for ACM journals in 2021/22 (£998.37).	Data source for APC: Delta Think, as of 15 June 2023.
Bentham	2021	£0	Number of 2021 OA articles published by organisations subscribing in 2022 (0), multiplied by half the APC spend for 2019 and 2020 (£1309.60).	2022 publish fee equal to APC spend for 2019 and 2020 (used for approximate APC in 2021).
Thieme	2019	£2217.71	Number of 2019 OA articles published by organisations subscribing in 2020, 2021 or 2022 (1), multiplied by average Hybrid APC for Georg Thieme Verlag KG journals in 2018/19 (£2217.71).	Data source for APC: Delta Think, as of 15 June 2023.
IOP	2019	£96,168.00	Number of 2019 OA articles published by organisations subscribing in 2020 (50), multiplied by average Hybrid APC for IOP journals in 2019/20 (£1,923.36).	Data source for APC: Delta Think, as of 15 June 2023.
Optica	2021	£303,685.46	Known spend of participating organisations on Hybrid and Gold APCs in 2020 (\$364,803), converted to GBP at 2020 currency exchange rate (0.812324), and multiplied for inflation between 2020 and 2021 (1.024817) ¹⁸ .	

Publisher	Pre-TA Year	Estimated pre-TA APC expenditure	Calculated as	Notes
Radiological Society of North America	2020	£0	Number of 2020 OA articles published by organisations subscribing in 2021 or 2022 (0), multiplied by the APC spend of those organisations in 2019 (\$0).	APC payments in 2020 for organisations not available – 2019 APC spend used as approximate.
Royal Irish Academy	2020	£0	Number of 2020 OA articles published by organisations subscribing in 2021 or 2022 (0), multiplied by the APC spend of those organisations in 2019 (£0).	APC payments in 2020 for organisations not available – 2019 APC spend used as approximate.
Taylor & Francis	2020	£605,812.71	Known spend of participating organisations on APCs in 2019 (£599,693.39), multiplied for inflation between 2019 and 2020 (1.0102) ¹⁹ .	

To ensure a fair comparison, only institutions that subscribed to the pre-TA agreement and the current agreement have been included, and only publishers with a subscription agreement (ie, not a TA) later than 2018 but before their TA were included (thereby excluding Springer Nature).

Actual cost savings

We calculated actual cost savings as the difference between the fee for the TA and the subscription expenditure plus expenditure on APCs by subscribing institutions in the year immediately prior to the TA.

Cost avoidance

Cost avoidance was calculated as the difference between the modelled hypothetical charge of read-only agreements and the modelled cost of the TA.

The dataset modelled costs for the future price increases of TAs, where there are annual increases for multi-year agreements as identified in the offer documents available on LSM. If multiple price list increases were offered, an average has been used in the dataset. In the instances where price list increases are not specified on the offer document (17 out of 38 publishers), 0% has been used.

To model the hypothetical charges for read-only agreements, had they continued, the percent price increase identified in the EBSCO Serial Price Projections Report 2019-2023 is used²⁰. As the report for 2024 has not yet been released, increases were assumed to be the same as 2023. To model the hypothetical charges for APCs for articles without UKRI or Wellcome funding and that are estimated to have not been published through the Green route (referred to as 'unfunded, non-Green APCs'), paid alongside read-only agreements, we used the percent price increase identified for APCs on all journals from Delta Think²¹. As the increase for 2023/24 is not yet available, increases were assumed to be the same as 2022/23. For some publishers it is not possible to split out the read and publish fee in 2022; these publishers have been omitted from the cost avoidance analysis²².

Any reference to published research output under the TAs refers to the collected and cleaned data obtained from publishers by Jisc for publishing via OA publishing agreements by subscribing institutions. Any reference to funded research output refers to UKRI or Wellcome funding as identified by Crossref for these published articles. Therefore, unfunded research output refers to articles without UKRI or Wellcome funding. Where publishers did not provide this data, we have excluded them from the cost avoidance analyses²³.

Offsetting

Offset is estimated as the proportion of modelled costs of the TA 'offset' by the value of articles published²⁴.

Limitations

The total number of subscribers to a TA may be higher than used in this analysis. All spend and savings figures shown are based on the institutions that subscribed to the pre-TA agreement and the current agreement, and therefore underestimate the actual spend figures.

As price increases for read-only subscription fees in 2024 and APCs in 2023/34 were assumed to be the same as in the previous year, and price increases for 17 agreements were assumed to be 0%, this report may be under- or over-reporting the estimated, modelled hypothetical charges of read-only subscriptions plus APC payments and/or the modelled cost of TAs, and therefore under- or over-reporting the cost avoidance by TAs.

As not all publishers and their corresponding agreements and subscriptions have been included (Springer Nature is excluded across the cost analyses, three publishers [including T&F]) are excluded from cost avoidance calculations and three publishers are excluded from analysis of offsetting), the analysis does not demonstrate the financial implications for all TAs. Figures shown in this report therefore under-report cost, actual cost savings and cost avoidance, and are not representative for offsetting proportions.

Financial dependence on block grants

This analysis aimed to ascertain the sector's current financial dependence on UKRI open access block grant (OABG) funding and estimate the sector's future financial dependence on it in the next few years.

Data sources

- Internal documents containing TA publisher lists, information on TA fees and fee/price list increases
- UKRI OABG returns for 2015-22
- Openly available online versions of TA contracts
- Licence subscriptions manager (LSM)
- Publisher-provided article-level metadata (ALM)

Articles charged to UKRI OABG

Institutions' OABG returns were cleaned by UKRI and then provided to us at Jisc where we did further work, including: merging records with duplicate DOIs, standardising institution and publisher names, and adding organisation IDs and Jisc bands. The data was filtered to selected TA publishers (see [figure 38](#)) and then summarised as article counts per publisher, per institution, per year.

As earlier checks revealed some potentially unexpected gaps in article records for 2021-22, for any publisher-institution pair with zero articles detected for 2021 and/or 2022 the annual count was set to the median annual article count from years 2015 to 2022. In the event that an institution failed to (fully) report to UKRI in 2021-22, this mitigates resultant skewing in error of the estimates for either 2022 spend or forecasted post-2022 spend, thereby increasing the robustness of the analysis.

UKRI OABG spend in 2022

Lists of subscribing institutions for each TA publisher and their subscription option were derived from LSM. Using the calculated article counts per year described above, additional data from LSM, information from the TA offer documents, TA price list increases and additional information recorded by Jisc's licensing managers (LMs), 2022 spend from UKRI BGs was calculated for each subscribing institution for each TA publisher as follows:

- For publishers where the TA fee is based on subscription spend only²⁵, the BG spend in 2022 was determined as £0 due to the absence of a publisher-specific element within TA spend
- For publishers where the online version of the TA contract listed both a specific subscription calculation and a means of separating publish vs read fees²⁶, the BG spend in 2022 was manually calculated from available data to match as closely as possible the method specified in the contract. Where specified, this calculation also factored in annual increases up to and including 2022, changes in the proportion of publish vs read fee elements and any specified variations to the calculation based on the institution's subscription option and/or publish rate
- For all remaining TA publishers, the BG spend in 2022 was determined as the summed publish fee listed in LSM. Annual increases were presumed to have been already applied up to and including 2022

- One publisher²⁷ was excluded from this and subsequent analysis due to insufficient available data
- Finally, for each publisher the calculated 2022 spend was summed across all institutions

Forecasted article counts chargeable to UKRI block grant (2023 – 2025)

Forecasting was performed independently for each TA publisher. First, for a given publisher, article counts per year between 2015 and 2022 (as described above) were summed across all institutions.

Where the article count for a given year was null, this might plausibly be due either to an erroneous gap in reporting or to a zero-article count. Instances of the latter should be retained for forecasting purposes, while instances of the former would incorrectly skew forecasting. Based on the assumption that an unexpectedly large jump above zero articles within a single year suggests that the zero-count is more likely an instance of non-reporting rather than a genuine zero, any zero-count that increases by $z > 5$ in the following year (where z is the converted z-score of absolute difference in article count for a given year relative to the previous year) was flagged as an outlier, and removed from the data along with any neighbouring zero-counts in consecutive years. This outlier criterion was selected as a more conservative option than using the standard $z > 3$, noting the small sample size and considering that there are likely to be larger fluctuations in neighbouring years than the normal distribution would predict especially, but not exclusively, due to COVID-19-related irregularities in the (inter) national publishing landscape.

Next, where there were fewer than three datapoints of article counts per year, the values for all missing years were replaced with the median of the available datapoints. This prevents the change from a single pair of consecutive years being extrapolated as a consistent year-on-year trend, given that small fluctuations are expected and not necessarily reflective of a consistent trend across a larger number of years.

A linear trend was fitted across all available article count datapoints from 2015 to 2022 using least squares polynomial fit. Then, we extrapolated this trend to produce estimated article counts in the years 2023, 2024 and 2025. We also calculated the multiplier value of annual growth relative to the previous year.

Projected UKRI block grant spend (2023-25)

For all publishers, projected future spend was derived from the calculated 2022 spend multiplied by the annual price increase(s) where listed for 2023 and 2024. As 2025 falls outside the listed price increases we have assumed that the annual increase for 2025 would match 2024's increase.

Additionally, for publishers where APC spend is factored into the TA fee²⁸ the 2022 spend was multiplied by the annual article growth relative to the previous year when calculating the projected spend for 2023, 2024 and 2025 to reflect presumed increases in pricing on hypothetical renewal of TAs within this period.

Limitations

This analysis was built on a number of assumptions for simplicity and due to data availability and quality constraints. Some major limitations are outlined below.

The analysis assumes that the UKRI OABG is used in the way outlined in UKRI's guidance on how to use the OABG for transformative agreements²⁹. However, institutions may, in practice, have been able to use the block grant for a wider set of expenditures related to TAs, particularly those TAs that had a publish fee based solely on previous subscription spend, which we have excluded for the purposes of this analysis. Some of the larger publishers³⁰ fell into this category, which could result in an underestimation of the sector's dependence on the UKRI OABG to cover the costs of TAs.

Article counts were sourced from UKRI OABG returns. However, these returns include more articles than may have been strictly eligible to go through TAs, and articles in a publisher's non-TA titles may also have been included. We used these article counts for a small proportion of publishers when calculating the 2022 OABG spend, and for all publishers when forecasting spend in 2023 to 2025. As the analysis seeks to evaluate TAs specifically, the number of in-scope articles published and resulting estimated/forecasted spend may therefore be overestimated.

Some of the calculations required to determine the publishing fee as outlined in the TA offer documentation were complex, and sometimes included references to specific, unknown figures. We used available data where relevant, but some elements of publishing fee calculations are unaccounted due to lack of available data, affecting

calculations of BG spend in 2022 and having resulting knock-on effects on the estimated spend in 2023 to 2025. For example, the analysis does not factor in caps on the number of articles permitted through some TAs. Additionally, the TA for IOP specified that one of two different calculations should be used to determine a given institution's fee, dependent on the institution's subscription option. The analysis simplified this by taking the publish fee from LSM regardless of subscription option, as it was not clear how the stated agreement options in LSM mapped to the two calculation options stated in the agreement.

Forecasting could not be performed directly upon financial spend, because only one robust datapoint (for the year 2022) was available. Instead, article counts were forecast and then converted to financial spend. This extra degree of separation inflates the level of uncertainty in our predictions.

The article counts covered the years 2015 to 2022, which provided a maximum of eight datapoints for prediction. However, this is a very small sample size for forecasting, making it difficult to pick out the overall trend among inconsequential fluctuations that are to be expected in real-world data. This is especially concerning as publishing rates have been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which saw dramatic short-term irregularities (potentially yet to be levelled out). Undue influence of 'noisy' data has been partially mitigated by removing what we estimate to be false zero-article counts and choosing a simple (ie, linear) model for forecasting. Nonetheless, confidence in the forecasting analysis should still be considered as relatively low.

The forecast also did not account for the impact of any publisher mergers or acquisitions between 2015 and 2022, which would be expected to raise the article counts. This forecast therefore over-inflates the rate of expected increase in publishing counts and therefore expected increase in dependence on the UKRI OABG.

The forecast factors in growth in publishing, on the assumptions that TAs would be renewed during the forecasting period, and that – for any TAs where the fee depends to some extent on APCs – the pricing structure would increase, not just with inflation but also by publishing growth. If that assumption were not the case, the forecast could represent an overestimation of future BG dependence.

While limited, this forecast provides an important indication of the potential growth in financial dependence on the UKRI OABG, which in conjunction with the elements of the cost analysis can be used to assess the financial effectiveness of TAs.

Assessment of funder compliance, transparency and workflows

All TA publishers identified in [figure 38](#) were assessed against specific criteria and research questions in sections 3b, 3c and 3d.

Section 3b

- Do authors retain rights to deposit AAM with CC BY?
- Is the default licence CC BY?
- Has the publisher joined Jisc's Publications Router?
- Does the publisher deposit articles to PubMed Central (PMC)/Europe PMC (EPMC)?

Section 3c

- In which cases have publishers ensured and provided transparency over publishing costs?
- To what extent have publishers provided clear roadmaps over their route to OA?
- Are publishers globally and systematically offsetting subscription/read revenue against OA revenues?

Section 3d

- What impact have TAs and TA workflows had for OA administrators and authors?

We based our assessment on information gathered from the following sources:

- LMs – Jisc staff who manage the individual TAs
- LSM
- TA publishers
- TA publisher websites
- A sample of Jisc member institutions that participate in the TAs

LMs used their expert knowledge and information recorded in LSM to answer questions relating to sections 3b, 3c and 3d for the agreements for which they are responsible. These responses were recorded on a summary spreadsheet. Pre-defined answer options were included where possible to provide quantitative data.

All publishers of TAs being reviewed were invited to complete a survey including questions (open and closed) relating to sections 3b, 3c and 3d³¹. Responses were recorded in a spreadsheet. Results included both quantitative and qualitative data.

Three institutions were invited to provide case studies relating to sections 3a, 3b, 3c and 3d. Those institutions were selected based on convenience sampling (they had responded to requests for volunteers in a strategic group meeting) and were a roughly representative sample of different-sized universities according to Jisc banding and UKRI OABG award – UCL (band 1), University of Lancaster (band 5A), Edge Hill University (band 6). Each institution completed a case study template including a list of questions³² and their answers provided qualitative information. A follow-up interview gave us an opportunity to clarify their responses.

Two publisher case study candidates were identified via website research relating to section 3c research questions on cost transparency and we carried out semi-structured interviews based on website content. A third was identified through LM expert knowledge. A close study was conducted of pricing information published online and information (all qualitative) was recorded in publishers' case study templates as good practice examples of transparency.

Limitations

The publisher survey was open for a short time – just three weeks. While extensions were granted to the publishers that requested them, this time period may have affected the response rate (21/38).

Along with the survey we provided an information sheet to describe the survey's purpose and how responses were going to be used. Some respondents may have interpreted survey questions differently than was intended, which may affect the meaningfulness of the results.

Although all questions included a free text area as an opportunity to provide further detail, this field was not mandatory. In cases where optional further information was not provided this may have limited the level of understanding.

The sample of institutional case studies was intended to provide a representative view of Jisc members; limiting the sample to three institutions may not have captured the full breadth of experiences. As the case studies were selected from Jisc's strategic groups, and based on volunteers, they are more likely to represent institutions with stronger opinions (positive or negative) on TAs than others.

Appendix 3: number and proportion of global and UK articles by Open Access status

Data source: Dimensions, see “[Appendix 2: methodologies](#)” for more information.

Number of global articles

OA status	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Gold (only)	290,373	379,647	464,648	590,308	739,583	893,504	1,098,041	1,248,726	1,299,312
Gold and Green (estimated)	258,477	310,133	348,071	405,065	464,197	588,221	648,691	640,543	557,615
Green (only)	267,086	280,748	303,796	314,424	317,939	308,502	333,283	320,115	231,657
Hybrid and Green (estimated)	51,659	57,647	64,508	68,101	72,934	67,792	101,766	135,602	158,199
Hybrid (only)	96,001	110,047	126,529	137,279	151,134	162,786	212,688	279,865	367,129
Bronze	385,574	377,008	401,346	412,294	417,350	417,656	459,065	468,168	434,163
Closed	1,908,319	1,894,139	1,896,756	1,965,456	1,992,767	2,007,996	2,023,933	2,094,804	2,152,224

Proportion of global articles

OA status	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Gold (only)	8.9%	11.1%	12.9%	15.2%	17.8%	20.1%	22.5%	24.1%	25.0%
Gold and Green (estimated)	7.9%	9.1%	9.7%	10.4%	11.2%	13.2%	13.3%	12.4%	10.7%
Green (only)	8.2%	8.2%	8.4%	8.1%	7.7%	6.9%	6.8%	6.2%	4.5%
Hybrid and Green (estimated)	1.6%	1.7%	1.8%	1.8%	1.8%	1.5%	2.1%	2.6%	3.0%
Hybrid (only)	3.0%	3.2%	3.5%	3.5%	3.6%	3.7%	4.4%	5.4%	7.1%
Bronze	11.8%	11.1%	11.1%	10.6%	10.0%	9.4%	9.4%	9.0%	8.4%
Closed	58.6%	55.6%	52.6%	50.5%	48.0%	45.2%	41.5%	40.4%	41.4%

Number of UK articles

OA status	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Gold (only)	17,120	20,979	22,574	26,046	28,291	31,331	40,549	46,421	45,989
Gold and Green (estimated)	5,108	6,271	6,761	7,816	8,507	11,904	13,551	16,027	13,936
Green (only)	33,397	40,116	52,576	57,503	59,077	58,717	56,907	50,314	31,055
Hybrid and Green (estimated)	10,421	12,906	16,643	16,259	17,029	15,511	21,361	24,060	25,351
Hybrid (only)	2,492	3,677	5,560	6,296	7,574	9,497	12,852	15,903	18,562
Bronze	19,503	19,716	19,470	19,807	21,784	19,527	21,716	19,691	11,983
Closed	78,543	72,221	59,030	51,976	49,991	53,662	53,553	56,210	60,278

Proportion of UK articles

OA status	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Gold (only)	10.3%	11.9%	12.4%	14.0%	14.7%	15.7%	18.4%	20.3%	22.2%
Gold and Green (estimated)	3.1%	3.6%	3.7%	4.2%	4.4%	6.0%	6.2%	7.0%	6.7%
Green (only)	20.1%	22.8%	28.8%	31.0%	30.7%	29.3%	25.8%	22.0%	15.0%
Hybrid and Green (estimated)	6.3%	7.3%	9.1%	8.8%	8.9%	7.8%	9.7%	10.5%	12.2%
Hybrid (only)	1.5%	2.1%	3.0%	3.4%	3.9%	4.7%	5.8%	7.0%	9.0%
Bronze	11.7%	11.2%	10.7%	10.7%	11.3%	9.8%	9.9%	8.6%	5.8%
Closed	47.2%	41.1%	32.3%	28.0%	26.0%	26.8%	24.3%	24.6%	29.1%

Appendix 4: detailed analysis of cost savings by publisher

The table on the following pages shows the pre-TA sector known expenditure on subscription fees and APCs; the sector expenditure on the first year total fee of the TA and the sector savings by publisher.

Data sources: Jisc's LSM and publisher-provided pre-TA APC expenditure.

* As noted in [appendix 2: methodologies](#), subscribers are limited to institutions that subscribed to the pre-TA agreement and the current agreement. The total number of subscribers to the TA may be higher.

Publisher	Start year	APC spend year prior to TA	Subs. fee year prior to TA	Subs. fee + APC spend year prior to TA	TA fee total (first year)	Savings	% saving	Subscribers to agreement*	Average savings / institution
American Chemical Society	2022	£112,900.00	£2,892,986.56	£3,005,886.56	£3,605,279.76	-£599,393.20	-20%	80	-£7,492.42
American Institute of Physics	2021	£80,428.43	£782,208.29	£862,636.72	£696,939.28	£165,697.44	19%	29	£5,713.70
American Physiological Society	2021	£28,659.63	£222,570.61	£251,230.24	£257,844.01	-£6,613.77	-3%	27	-£244.95
Association for Computing Machinery	2020	£998.37	£11,411.68	£12,410.05	£26,495.07	-£14,085.02	-113%	3	-£4,695.01
Bentham	2022	£0	£793.03	£793.03	£7,275.55	-£6,482.52	-817%	1	-£6,482.52
Bioscientifica	2020	£13,500.00	£86,089.00	£99,589.00	£76,099.00	£23,490.00	24%	14	£1,677.86
BMJ Publishing	2021	£1,302,786.31	£452,441.00	£1,755,227.31	£876,962.93	£878,264.38	50%	59	£14,885.84
Cambridge University Press	2021	£532,398.51	£2,481,487.32	£3,013,885.83	£2,548,091.21	£465,794.62	15%	115	£4,050.39
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press	2021	£25,074.39	£108,542.82	£133,617.21	£130,917.77	£2,699.44	2%	14	£192.82
Elsevier	2022	£7,227,937.74	£43,293,884.29	£50,521,822.03	£38,662,654.30	£11,859,167.73	23%	151	£78,537.53
European Respiratory Society	2020	£8,115.20	£8,200.00	£16,315.20	£25,640.00	-£9,324.80	-57%	10	-£932.48

Publisher	Start year	APC spend year prior to TA	Subs. fee year prior to TA	Subs. fee + APC spend year prior to TA	TA fee total (first year)	Savings	% saving	Subscribers to agreement*	Average savings / institution
Future Science	2021	£4,997.00	£56,382.00	£61,379.00	£61,199.00	£180.00	0%	7	£25.71
Georg Thieme	2020	£2,217.71	£48,610.41	£50,828.12	£54,702.86	-£3,874.74	-8%	4	-£968.69
IOP Publishing	2020	£96,168.00	£1,595,207.18	£1,691,375.18	£1,748,608.35	-£57,233.17	-3%	51	-£1,122.22
IWA Publishing	2020	£7,351.57	£89,383.85	£96,735.42	£92,338.00	£4,397.42	5%	11	£399.77
John Benjamins.	2022	£12,287.37	£20,467.12	£32,754.49	£23,140.46	£9,614.03	29%	9	£1,068.23
Koninklijke Brill	2021	£8,822.79	£342,671.75	£351,494.54	£322,197.57	£29,296.97	8%	36	£813.80
Microbiology Society	2020	£70,194.71	£150,046.00	£220,240.71	£179,760.36	£40,480.35	18%	42	£963.82
National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America	2021	£59,774.51	£20,556.14	£80,330.65	£52,610.41	£27,720.24	35%	8	£3,465.03
Optica (previously Optical Society of America)	2022	£303,685.46	£338,101.00	£641,786.46	£155,487.19	£486,299.27	76%	21	£23,157.11
Oxford University Press	2021	£1,737,992.00	£3,461,436.56	£5,199,428.56	£4,776,629.59	£422,798.97	8%	76	£5,563.14
Portland Press	2020	£241,022.40	£159,246.26	£400,268.66	£212,399.00	£187,869.66	47%	34	£5,525.58
Radiological Society of North America	2021	£0	£2,077.21	£2,077.21	£2,816.06	-£738.85	-36%	1	-£738.85

Publisher	Start year	APC spend year prior to TA	Subs. fee year prior to TA	Subs. fee + APC spend year prior to TA	TA fee total (first year)	Savings	% saving	Subscribers to agreement*	Average savings / institution
Royal College of General Practitioners	2021	£10,000.00	£2,322.20	£12,322.20	£13,998.00	-£1,675.80	-14%	7	-£239.40
Royal Irish Academy	2021	£0	£856.00	£856.00	£1,358.00	-£502.00	-59%	2	-£251.00
Royal Society	2021	£220,266.00	£304,110.33	£524,376.33	£610,200.50	-£85,824.17	-16%	30	-£2,860.81
Royal Society of Chemistry	2020	£634,595.00	£1,091,017.00	£1,725,612.00	£1,845,339.92	-£119,727.92	-7%	61	-£1,962.75
S. Karger	2021	£83,637.34	£177,728.30	£261,365.64	£260,467.05	£898.59	0%	6	£149.77
Sage	2020	£195,656.00	£8,417,351.36	£8,613,007.36	£8,775,000.78	-£161,993.42	-2%	107	-£1,513.96
Taylor & Francis	2021	£605,812.71	£15,644,263.10	£16,250,075.81	£15,820,121.97	£429,953.84	3%	104	£4,134.17
The Company of Biologists	2020	£133,977.96	£302,994.00	£436,971.96	£459,690.98	-£22,719.02	-5%	41	-£554.12
The Geological Society of London	2021	£16,950.00	£127,654.03	£144,604.03	£166,743.99	-£22,139.96	-15%	26	-£851.54
The Rockefeller University	2020	£91,211.95	£201,875.80	£293,087.75	£187,828.00	£105,259.75	36%	26	£4,048.45
University of Bristol	2022	£4,500.00	£22,938.89	£27,438.89	£64,218.00	-£36,779.11	-134%	11	-£3,343.56
Walter de Gruyter	2021	£6,119.85	£174,412.25	£180,532.10	£197,264.37	-£16,732.27	-9%	10	-£1,673.23
Wiley	2020	£5,036,758.17	£18,064,747.71	£23,101,505.88	£21,224,399.69	£1,877,106.19	8%	146	£12,856.89
Wolters Kluwer	2022	£421,967.31	£1,151,368.86	£1,573,336.17	£711,363.58	£861,972.59	55%	14	£61,569.47

Appendix 5: publisher compliance with funder mandates

Data source: LSM, licensing manager intelligence and publisher websites.

Publisher (of product)	Do authors retain rights to deposit AAM with CC-BY?	Is default licence CC-BY?	Has publisher joined Publications Router?	Does publisher deposit articles to PMC/EPMC?
American Chemical Society	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
American Institute of Physics	No	Yes, for all journals	No	No, not applicable
American Physiological Society	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
Association for Computing Machinery	Yes, all journals	Yes, for some journals	No	No, not applicable
Bentham	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
Bioscientifica	Yes, all journals	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
BMJ Publishing	No	Yes, for some journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
Cambridge University Press	Yes, for some journals	Yes, for some journals	No	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
Elsevier	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
European Respiratory Society	Yes, for all journals*	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
Future Science	No	No	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
Thieme	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
IOP Publishing	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
IWA Publishing	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles

Publisher (of product)	Do authors retain rights to deposit AAM with CC-BY?	Is default licence CC-BY?	Has publisher joined Publications Router?	Does publisher deposit articles to PMC/EPMC?
John Benjamins	Yes, for all journals	Yes, for all journals	No	No, not applicable
Brill	Yes, for all journals	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
Microbiology Society	Yes, for all journals	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
National Academy of Sciences of the USA	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
Optica	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
Oxford University Press	No	Yes, for some journals	Yes	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
Portland Press	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
Radiological Society of North America	Yes, for some journals*	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
Royal College of General Practitioners	Yes, for all journals	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
Royal Irish Academy	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
Royal Society	Yes, for all journals	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
Royal Society of Chemistry	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, only articles where funder mandates require deposit and an APC is paid for Gold OA
S. Karger	Yes, for all journals	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
Sage	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit

Publisher (of product)	Do authors retain rights to deposit AAM with CC-BY?	Is default licence CC-BY?	Has publisher joined Publications Router?	Does publisher deposit articles to PMC/EPMC?
Springer Nature	Yes, for all journals [†]	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
Taylor & Francis	No	No	No	Yes, all articles where funder mandates deposit
The Company of Biologists	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
The Geological Society of London	No	Yes, for all journals	No	No, not applicable
The Rockefeller University	No	Yes, for all journals	No	Yes, all eligible articles
University of Bristol	Yes, for all journals	Yes, for all journals	No	No, not applicable
Walter de Gruyter	No	Yes, for all journals	Yes	Yes, only articles where funder mandates require deposit and an APC is paid for Gold OA
Wiley	No	No	Yes	Yes, all eligible articles
Wolters Kluwer	No	Yes, for some journals	No	Yes, only articles where funder mandates require deposit (NIH only) or an APC is paid for Gold OA

* ERS and the RSNA permit funder-compliant Green OA via AAM only for authors whose funders require it.

[†] Springer Nature permits funder-compliant Green OA via AAM only for CAs whose affiliated institutions have signed up to the Jisc TA.

Appendix 6: publisher transparency

Data source: publisher survey responses and publisher websites.

Publisher	Roadmap charting transition to OA?	Information in public domain?	Timeline for transition to OA?
Association for Computing Machinery	Yes	Yes ³³	Yes, 1 January 2026
BMJ Publishing	Unable to disclose	Not applicable	Unable to disclose
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press	Yes	Yes ³⁴	Yes, 31 December 2024
Cambridge University Press	Yes	Partial ³⁵	Yes, 2027
European Respiratory Society	Unable to disclose	Not applicable	Unable to disclose
IOP Publishing	Yes	Partial ³⁶	Unable to disclose
IWA Publishing	Not applicable	Not applicable	OA since 2021
John Benjamins	Yes	No	No
Microbiology Society	Unable to disclose	Not applicable	Unable to disclose
Optica	No	Not applicable	Not applicable
Portland Press	Yes	Partial ³⁷	Yes, 28 February 2025
Royal College of General Practitioners	No	Not applicable	Not applicable
Royal Society	Yes	Partial ³⁸	No
Royal Society of Chemistry	Yes	Yes ³⁹	Yes, 2028
S. Karger	No	Not applicable	Not applicable
Taylor & Francis	Yes	Partial ⁴⁰	No
The Company of Biologists	Yes	Yes ⁴¹	2025/26
The Geological Society of London	Yes	Partial ⁴²	No
Walter de Gruyter	Yes	No	2027 (tbc)
Wiley	Unable to disclose	Not applicable	Unable to disclose
Wolters Kluwer	Unable to disclose	Not applicable	Unable to disclose

Appendix 7: availability of publisher TA dashboards

Data source: licensing manager intelligence.

Publisher (of product)	Is there a TA dashboard?
American Chemical Society	Yes, publisher dashboard
American Institute of Physics	Yes, publisher dashboard
American Physiological Society	No
Association for Computing Machinery	Yes, publisher dashboard
Bentham	No
Bioscientifica	No
BMJ Publishing	Yes, RightsLink
Cambridge University Press	Yes, RightsLink
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press	No
Elsevier	Yes, publisher dashboard
European Respiratory Society	No
Future Science	Yes, RightsLink
Thieme	Yes, RightsLink
IOP Publishing	No
IWA Publishing	No
John Benjamins	No
Brill	Yes, RightsLink
Microbiology Society	Yes, RightsLink
National Academy of Sciences of the USA	Yes, RightsLink
Optica	Yes, RightsLink
Oxford University Press	Yes, publisher dashboard
Portland Press	Yes, RightsLink
Radiological Society of North America	No
Royal College of General Practitioners	No
Royal Irish Academy	No
Royal Society	Yes, RightsLink
Royal Society of Chemistry	Yes, RightsLink
S. Karger	Yes, ChronosHub
Sage	Yes, publisher dashboard

Publisher (of product)	Is there a TA dashboard?
Springer Nature	Yes, publisher dashboard
Taylor & Francis	Yes, publisher dashboard
The Company of Biologists	No
The Geological Society of London	No
The Rockefeller University	No
University of Bristol	No
Walter de Gruyter	Yes, RightsLink
Wiley	Yes, publisher dashboard
Wolters Kluwer	Yes, RightsLink

Appendix 8: institutional case studies

The following case studies provide snapshots of institutional experiences and views of transitional agreements and the extent to which they fulfil the sector's TA requirements.

The template completed by the case study institutions can be found in the [Jisc repository](#).

Case study one – University College London

Institutional profile

UCL is a multidisciplinary university, with more than 16,000 staff and 50,000 students from over 150 different countries. In the latest Research Excellence Framework assessment, REF 2021, UCL came second in research power only to Oxford (1st) and maintained their leading position in medicine, health and life sciences as well as social sciences.

Requirement one: cost savings

Q1. Do you currently participate or have you participated in TAs that cost your institution more than your previous subscription and APC expenditure with the same publisher? If yes, please also answer Q2.

Answer:

Yes

Q2. Please provide a brief summary of your internal decision-making process to explain how and why you chose to participate in TAs that did not reduce costs for your institution.

Answer:

We considered the following factors in deciding to participate in the ACM agreement:

1. Financial data, including investment per article under the agreement and APC list price.
2. The amount of the cost that could be allocated to our open access block grants, based on previous publishing and the costs in 1 (above).
3. The availability of funds in our subscription budgets to cover the additional costs that cannot be paid from our open access block grants.
4. The likelihood of more agreements of this type being offered in the current year.

1. The extent to which Jisc considers that the publisher has been transparent with its costings.
2. The type of model, whether it envisages a full flip, and the extent to which Jisc supports it.
3. The likelihood of other institutions participating.
4. The publisher's contingency plans if the target number of participating institutions is not reached.
5. The availability of an opt-out

Requirements two and three: transitionality and funder compliance

Q1. Since engaging with TAs, what measures, if any, has your institution taken to adjust to agreement models based on paying for publishing services rather than read access?

Answer:

We have made administrative changes to allow us to streamline payments for publishing services, including:

- Setting up a new budget from which to pay the elements of publishing fees that are covered by our subscription funds rather than by our open access block grants. This allows us to ensure that VAT is paid correctly
- Adjusting our payment processes so that separate purchase orders are raised by the Open Access Team and the E-resources (Subscriptions) team where contributions are being made both from subscriptions and open access budgets
- Sought additional institutional funding to cover VAT on the publish element of read and publish agreements
- Introduced administrative changes to enable the Open Access and E-resources (Subscriptions) teams to manage contributions to the agreements
- Introduced processes to analyse publishing through transformative agreements and inform contributions from open access block grants

Q2. To what extent does your institutional budget provide flexibility to move funds from recurrent subscription spend to cover costs for fully OA agreements, including supporting 'Diamond' OA models where there is no subscription or publishing fee?

Answer:

We only have limited flexibility for this in our institutional budgets. We have a small fully open access budget that we have used to part-pay for the PLOS and JMIR agreements, and for two diamond OA agreements. However, this budget is usually insufficient to pay for all unfunded research papers in fully OA journals with a UCL corresponding author, so there is only limited funding to pay for agreements except where we were previously funding articles in fully OA journals (this would apply if, for example, a Frontiers or BMC TA became available).

There is interest in supporting diamond OA, but current budgets may not be sufficient for it if a large number of agreements were offered. At present, our criteria for funding diamond OA require there to be a UCL connection (e.g., UCL academics on a relevant editorial board) or UCL publishing in the venue in question. We have joined two OACF agreements on this basis.

Subscription budgets cannot normally be repurposed to pay the costs of fully OA or diamond agreements, though if substantial savings were made on subscription costs this might be possible. We have used subscription funds to support diamond open access agreements that cover content that we would previously have paid for had it not been open access. Underspends in our subscription budget can occasionally be used to fund deposits to fully OA publishers, but this cannot be relied on.

Q3. How much of your institution's 2022 TA spend is paid from research funder block grants? Please provide a total amount and an amount for each of the TAs you currently participate in.

Answer:

Table 1: Total amount

Funder	Total 2022 funder contribution on all TAs		
	2021/2022 grant year	2022/2023 grant year	Total
British Heart Foundation	£35,895.11	£0 for 2022 TAs	£35,895.11
Cancer Research UK	£62,259.95	£0 for 2022 TAs	£62,259.95
UKRI	£44,672.57	£861,609.21	£906,281.79
Wellcome	£282,365.10	£0 for 2022 TAs	£282,365.10

Table 2: Per transitional agreement (For calendar year 2022)

	British Heart Foundation	Cancer Research UK	UKRI	Wellcome
TA name	Amount claimed from funder in 2022			
American Chemical Society			£29,812.15	
American Physiological Society	£2,163.40		£1,699.82	£3,863.22
Bioscientifica			£1,102.02	£1,585.82
BMJ Publishing	£2,897.85	£3,311.83	£24,061.33	£12,419.34
Cambridge University Press			£44,634.37	£10,521.00
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press				£3,553.88
The Company of Biologists	£1,120.18	£653.44	£4,667.40	£2,893.79
Walter de Gruyter			£1,611.17	
Future Science			£1,594.80	
Institute of Physics			£20,776.82	
IWA Publishing			£991.20	
Microbiology Society			£2,104.88	

	British Heart Foundation	Cancer Research UK	UKRI	Wellcome
Optica			£17,014.70	£2,320.19
Oxford University Press	£6,885.39	£9,388.39	£126,429.76	£45,064.28
Portland Press			£3,496.22	£929.38
Royal Society			£19,433.75	£3,980.41
Royal Society of Chemistry		£1,352.21	£63,553.81	£2,704.42
Sage	£877.01		£12,662.19	£4,000.00
Springer Compact	£7,770.19	£11,655.29	£137,920.99	£36,908.43
Taylor & Francis Q1/2 2022 (Additional charges for Qs 3/4 will be made in due course, through budget transfers)			£8,670.20	£2127.60
University of Bristol Press			£1,791.90	
Wiley	£2,127.79	£27,320.00	£269,963.90	£80,276.11
Wolters Kluwer	£11,827.24		£19,219.27	£18,233.68

Q4. How is your institution anticipating dealing with the loss of funding contribution in the event of both UKRI and Wellcome withdrawing OA funding for TAs at the end of 2024? Please indicate if you are planning any of the following examples or add any other ideas you have had.

Answer:

Example	Please note if examples apply to your institution
Participating only in TAs with publishers that your affiliated authors publish most with	Yes.
Exploring alternative compliance routes, e.g., rights retention, and not participating in TAs	Yes.
Increasing institutional investment in TAs	Unlikely.

Requirement four: transparency

Q1. How did/would access to this type of cost transparency information⁴³ affect your institution's decision making when considering joining TAs?

Answer:

It is difficult for us to assess the information provided even by publishers like PLOS and ACM, because we are not accountants or experts on publishing business models. The same is true of contextual information provided about publishers' business models, for instance in the BMJ and Sage offers. It is useful, but we do not know how much weight or credence to give it.

In general, we rely on Jisc's recommendations on publishers' business models and their appropriateness for investment. PLOS's blog post and ACM's slides give us some confidence that their models have been properly costed, that these publishers are serious (in the case of ACM) about transitioning to a gold OA model and that their objective is not to make an unreasonable profit at the expense of authors and institutions. PLOS's transparency about its Community Action model enabled us to participate in this agreement despite its relatively high investment per article. We have not registered with the Journal Comparison Service.

As yet, we have not been in a position in which we have had to make choices about which transformative agreements to take. Being a very large research-intensive institution, with very large numbers of UKRI/Wellcome-funded papers, it has made sense for us to participate in most of the agreements on offer. If we were to find ourselves unable to use UKRI funds to support transformative agreements, we would need to look more carefully at publishers' business models, but we would still be very circumscribed by the affordability of the agreements. Signing up to the ACM agreement was quite a difficult decision given the level of additional cost, and we would struggle to find extra funds for similar agreements unless we could use UKRI funds.

Q2. What else would give your institution confidence that publishers are splitting out different revenue components and aren't double-charging for the same services – eg, levying publishing charges (APCs) for publications in hybrid journals while not providing a proportionate decrease in subscription costs?

Answer:

- An assessment from Jisc, as part of an offer, that they have considered the data that the publisher has provided and that it provides satisfactory assurances
- Evidence that the publisher is flipping hybrid journals to fully OA, as opposed to launching new fully OA and/or hybrid journals. Some publishers have launched large numbers of new titles in recent years. We presume that funds from the APCs that institutions have paid on top of subscription fees has contributed to the costs of these launches

Requirement five: efficiencies

Q1. To what extent have TAs delivered efficiencies at your institution when compared to managing OA payments outside an agreement? Please explain your answer and highlight any workflow areas requiring further improvements that would increase efficiencies.

Answer:

We have for many years maintained a number of prepayment agreements with publishers that have allowed us to pay for APCs in fully open access journals (and, previously, hybrid journals) without the administrative burden of invoicing. From a very simple standpoint, transformative agreements provide similar efficiencies, because they avoid our having to raise requisitions, receipt purchase orders, record invoice numbers, liaise with UCL Accounts Payable, provide proofs of payment and reconcile invoice transactions (particularly onerous in the case of foreign currency transactions). The data below illustrates the growth in the proportion of UCL APCs paid through transformative agreements between 2020 and 2022.

Row Labels	Invoice	Prepay	TA
2020	594	673	955
2021	601	576	1680
2022	371	369	2589

Central approval process like the ones used for transformative agreements (and prepayments), workflows for transformative agreements are not without problems and administrative burdens. Carrying out approvals and/or liaising with publishers for UCL’s 39 agreements (in 2023) is a relatively quick process, but requires a more advanced skill-set than previous APC payment workflows. We have changed our staffing arrangements accordingly, with higher-grade staff now dealing with approvals, and a manager who has responsibility for implementing and troubleshooting agreement workflows. The multiplicity of article types, publisher dashboards, funder policies and author statuses means that staff need to be adept at making judgements, and that it is difficult to achieve consistency even within a single institution. We have implemented special eligibility criteria for honorary and visiting staff, and for former students and staff, the latter in order to try to avoid approving papers without a significant UCL connection and baking these costs into future agreements. We have introduced special workflows for recording articles that are published gold OA through agreements, and for checking publisher reports. We have struggled to keep up with post-publication checks (CC BY and deposit in EPMC), and are hoping that we will be able to automate these, or rely on this being centralised through Jisc, in future. We maintain a large number of templates to help staff advise authors both about eligibility for the agreements and workflows for using them.

Some publishers' dashboards provide insufficient metadata, requiring us to liaise with authors to obtain accepted manuscripts or ask further questions before we can approve a paper. Some publishers' rejection reasons are misleading for authors, since they do not fit into the categories we use. Article types can be confusing; this, again, may necessitate our liaising directly with the corresponding author. Different publisher approaches to co-corresponding authorship and dual affiliations can make it difficult for us to advise authors. Smaller publishers tend to follow a more manual workflow than larger ones; this is generally not an issue, although it means that our records are not usually up to date.

We now maintain a number of spreadsheets in which we record the costs of each of our transformative agreements, contributions from funders' budgets, contributions from UCL's subscription budgets, the number of articles that used the previous year's agreement and other metrics. We use both [InCites](#) and our own data to decide in what proportions funders' budgets should contribute to the agreements. The subscriptions and open access teams liaise closely about payments. The need to raise purchase orders from different budgets, and/or transfer funds between budgets, has made the process of paying for agreements very complex.

Q2. Does your institution have any concerns about the reduction/removal of friction in the author workflow within TAs?

Answer:

Authors have become extremely familiar with the term 'transformative agreement', and often fail to appreciate the costs and complexity of the agreements. These agreements perpetuate existing models of publishing, and certainly do make it easier for authors who might not otherwise have published gold open access to do so, regardless of any funder requirement, without considering the cost.

Case study two – University of Lancaster

Institutional profile

Lancaster is a research-intensive university which is consistently ranked in the top 15 universities in the UK league tables. In the REF2021, 91% of their research was independently rated as ‘internationally excellent’ or ‘world leading’, including 46% rated in the highest category of 4*, and 99% of Lancaster’s overall research environment is rated world-leading or internationally excellent. This includes areas such as research support, training and facilities. It has also been awarded a Gold rating in the Teaching Excellence Framework (TEF) in 2023.

Requirement one: cost savings

Q1. Do you currently participate or have you participated in TAs that cost your institution more than your previous subscription and APC expenditure with the same publisher? If yes, please also answer Q2.

Answer:

Yes

Q2. Please provide a brief summary of your internal decision-making process to explain how and why you chose to participate in TAs that did not reduce costs for your institution.

Answer:

Where the cost is marginally more (no more than £3,000) we’ve signed up to ‘test the water’ with some smaller agreements hoping publication activity would increase and engagement with agreement will increase. This would also minimise our administrative costs and make processes easier for academics.

For some agreements where the gap is too large (eg, ACM) we would not sign up. This particular agreement had lots of ‘in the wild’ APCs so it would have meant the

Content and Scholarship budget would have had to pay over £12,000 difference for those in the wild unfunded APCs, which we deemed to be too expensive.

We tried to sign up to these agreements at times when we have had sufficient institutional budget available and when we had no budget constraints, but if we had had such constraints it would not be so easy to sign up to them.

Requirements two and three: transitionality and funder compliance

Q1. Since engaging with TAs, what measures, if any, has your institution taken to adjust to agreement models based on paying for publishing services rather than read access?

Answer:

We have changed the focus and even the name of our budget so that it is no longer just a subscription budget but now a Content and Scholarship budget to include OA publishing and initiatives. We’ve set this up and renamed it so that we are transparent to the university on what we’re actually paying for. We keep a record and monitor the amount we spend on read and publish separately.

Q2. To what extent does your institutional budget provide flexibility to move funds from recurrent subscription spend to cover costs for fully OA agreements, including supporting ‘diamond’ OA models where there is no subscription or publishing fee?

Answer:

We’ve been quite flexible, but we’ve been fortunate in that our budget hasn’t had a major cut and we’ve had the capacity to fund more of these models. We’ve made a positive, conscious decision to support these new OA models and initiatives as we can see the wider good.

Q3. How much of your institution's 2022 TA spend is paid from research funder block grants? Please provide a total amount and an amount for each of the TAs you currently participate in.

Answer:

Table 1: Total amount

Funder	Total 2022 funder contribution on all TAs		
	2021/2022 grant year	2022/2023 grant year	Total
British Heart Foundation	£0	£0	£0
Cancer Research UK	N/A	N/A	N/A
UKRI	£91,586.05	£277,557.99	£369,144.04
Wellcome	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 2: Per transitional agreement (For calendar year 2022)

	British Heart Foundation	Cancer Research UK	UKRI	Wellcome
TA name	Amount claimed from funder in 2022			
American Chemical Society	N/A	N/A	£0	N/A
American Institute of Physics Publishing	N/A	N/A	£0	N/A
BMJ Publishing (2/22)	N/A	N/A	£2,640	N/A
Cambridge University Press (12/22)	N/A	N/A	£8,263.32	N/A
The Company of Biologists	N/A	N/A	£0	N/A
Elsevier R&P (4/22) (12/22)	N/A	N/A	£58,155.17 £58,348.19	N/A
European Respiratory Society (12/22)	N/A	N/A	£738.60	N/A

	British Heart Foundation	Cancer Research UK	UKRI	Wellcome
The Geological Society Lyell Collection	N/A	N/A	£0	N/A
IOP Publishing	N/A	N/A	£0	N/A
IWA Publishing	N/A	N/A	£0	N/A
John Benjamins	N/A	N/A	£0	N/A
Oxford University Press (2/22)	N/A	N/A	£11,200	N/A
Portland Press (1/22) (12/22)	N/A	N/A	£525.60 £525.60	N/A

Q4. How is your institution anticipating dealing with the loss of funding contribution in the event of both UKRI and Wellcome withdrawing OA funding for TAs at the end of 2024? Please indicate if you are planning any of the following examples or add any other ideas you have had.

Answer:

We've implemented a rights retention policy so we should be able to be compliant anyway via the Green OA route. We may have to use more of our budget to pay for these in future, although it seems unlikely that we would be able to afford to cover the prior UKRI expenditure/contribution to these agreements.

Example	Please note if examples apply to your institution
Participating only in TAs with publishers that your affiliated authors publish most with	We do that now but we wouldn't be able to continue if our budget had to pay for everything – not sustainable
Exploring alternative compliance routes, eg, rights retention, and not participating in TAs	Yes – rights retention
Increasing institutional investment in TAs	No – we wouldn't be able to afford it

Requirement four: transparency

Q1. How did/would access to this type of cost transparency information affect your institution's decision making when considering joining TAs?

Answer:

It is absolutely crucial – if a TA isn't Jisc-approved and transparent then we would be taking backward steps and wouldn't know what each institution is paying, and for what.

UKRI determines that TAs must be Jisc-approved to be able to spend block grant so the only agreements we are signing up for are Jisc-approved ones. If a publisher contacts us that is offering an agreement that you haven't approved then we reply asking them to contact Jisc.

Q2. What else would give your institution confidence that publishers are splitting out different revenue components and aren't double-charging for the same services/ e.g. levying publishing charges (APCs) for publications in hybrid journals while not providing a proportionate decrease in subscription costs?

Answer:

It would be helpful if publishers are clearer on VAT elements but I'm not sure if this is really to do with double-charging (just a point worth noting that the VAT element can inflate the cost of a TA?). It is added to the publishing side which falsely inflates the overall cost (I'm thinking of Springer – a reduction in the overall cost and a great potential agreement but the reduction is not as large as we initially thought due to the VAT element).

A breakdown of the cost in full detail and providing full data behind accessing content and publication history, and costs apportioned to each would be helpful.

If it's a Jisc deal we have confidence that they will have asked these questions even if we don't receive full details/data.

Requirement five : efficiencies

Q1. To what extent have TAs delivered efficiencies at your institution when compared to managing OA payments outside an agreement? Please explain your answer and highlight any workflow areas requiring further improvements that would increase efficiencies.

Answer:

It offers a simple approval process for library staff in the OA team, although it does depend on the criteria and each publisher's workflow and dashboards as to the savings in administration. An automated workflow with some publishers makes it easier for our academics to take advantage of the agreements.

Case study three – Edge Hill University

Institutional profile

Since 1885, Edge Hill University has been inspiring minds and changing futures. Driven by its ethos of ‘creating opportunity from knowledge’ for more than 13,000 students who study on its award-winning campus. Today, Edge Hill is proudly one of the highest climbers in the Guardian Good University Guide 2024 – top 4 in the North West – and has been awarded gold for student experience, silver overall, in the Teaching Excellence Framework (TEF 2023). More than half of the University’s research is classed as ‘world-leading’ or ‘internationally excellent’ in the latest Research Excellence Framework (REF 2021), ensuring that education, from its student community to the global community, is far-reaching and has a truly transformative effect.

Requirement one: cost savings

Q1. Do you currently participate or have you participated in TAs that cost your institution more than your previous subscription and APC expenditure with the same publisher? If yes, please also answer Q2.

Answer:

No

Q2. Please provide a brief summary of your internal decision-making process to explain how and why you chose to participate in TAs that did not reduce costs for your institution.

Answer:

As a low publishing university, we haven’t seen a huge increase beyond what we would expect with inflation. The Covid rebates provided by some publishers in 2020/21 have made it quite hard to track exactly how much costs have increased. Although our publishing has grown, the rebates and other reductions secured by

Jisc have prevented costs escalating out of hand. Where agreements are more heavily weighted towards publishing costs then the application of VAT means we haven’t seen the benefits we expected from e-journals becoming VAT free in 2020.

Requirements two and three: transitionality and funder compliance

Q1. Since engaging with TAs, what measures, if any, has your institution taken to adjust to agreement models based on paying for publishing services rather than read access?

Answer:

We haven’t taken any formal measures to adjust for paying for models that are based on publishing services. Prior to TAs we funded big subscription journal deals from our subscriptions budget and we have continued to fund TAs using this budget as increases for the most part have been modest and manageable. If costs had risen more significantly then we might have needed to source supplementary funding from elsewhere in the university, but up until now this hasn’t been necessary.

This year Edge Hill was awarded a proportion of the UKRI block grant for the first time. Previously we have not been eligible and therefore we have never been reliant on using this to fund or part fund TAs. Although we have welcomed the allocation of block grant funding, utilising it to part pay the cost of a TA hasn’t always been straightforward and has required additional communications with Finance and the Research Office to ensure invoices are paid against the correct internal fund code.

We have found managing VAT to be one of the most challenging aspects of TAs, particularly as since 2020 this only applies to the publish element of the agreement. The amount of VAT we pay is tied to publishing volume and this can make budgeting particularly challenging as we never know quite how much we will need to pay. In the longer term this is a risk to libraries as the more we publish, the more VAT we pay, potentially diminishing progress that has been made around reducing and constraining costs.

Q2. To what extent does your institutional budget provide flexibility to move funds from recurrent subscription spend to cover costs for fully OA agreements, including supporting 'diamond' OA models where there is no subscription or publishing fee?

Answer:

Our subscription to PLOS was initially funded by the Research Office but payment for this is moving to the library going forward. We have some flexibility in our budget, but to date we haven't supported any other fully OA or 'diamond' journal models from the library budget (although we have used some of this budget to support community-based OA book memberships). The library is generally trusted to manage the resources budget as it sees fit with the expectation that we will support agreements that provide the university with value for money. Our Finance department are not overly concerned with understanding how a model works, so if we want to invest money in diamond OA models we can. The challenge has been finding the funds to support these types of models when so much of our budget is eaten up with recurrent subscription spend. We have just produced a two-year collections strategy and one of the recommendations that has been made is that we start to ring-fence a small proportion of the subscriptions budget to support community-based OA models including 'diamond' OA. In the future as TA agreements flip to a fully OA equivalent, we would anticipate the library continuing to fund and administer the agreements. There may need to be some reconfiguration of budgets to support this but what exactly this will look like we don't yet know.

A note on the ACM TA (point also relevant to requirement 4). Unlike other TAs which often do not seem to have a clear end point (ie, the point at which they have 'transitioned' to a fully OA model), ACM has an ambitious strategy for how and when it will flip to becoming a fully OA model. This agreement works for us as we do very little publishing in ACM titles, but it could be costly for higher output HEIs. However, the transparency of the approach and ACM's willingness to share their plan is commendable.

Q3. How much of your institution's 2022 TA spend is paid from research funder block grants? Please provide a total amount and an amount for each of the TAs you currently participate in.

Answer:

Edge Hill only received a block grant from UKRI for the first time in 22/23, a total of £8,421.85. We spent £2,220 of this to fund a subscription to SciFree and the remainder was used to fund a proportion of the publish element of three TAs (including VAT). Prior to this year TAs were fully funded from the library subscriptions budget.

Table 1: Total amount

Funder	Total 2022 funder contribution on all TAs		
	2021/2022 grant year	2022/2023 grant year	Total
British Heart Foundation	N/A	N/A	N/A
Cancer Research UK	N/A	N/A	N/A
UKRI	N/A	£6,201.85	£6,201.85
Wellcome	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 2: Per transitional agreement

	British Heart Foundation	Cancer Research UK	UKRI	Wellcome
TA name	Amount claimed from funder in 2022			
Wiley	N/A	N/A	£4,218.43	N/A
OUP	N/A	N/A	£1,281.94	N/A
Elsevier	N/A	N/A	£701.48	N/A

Q4. How is your institution anticipating dealing with the loss of funding contribution in the event of both UKRI and Wellcome withdrawing OA funding for TAs at the end of 2024? Please indicate if you are planning any of the following examples or add any other ideas you have had.

Answer:

The proportion of funded research at Edge Hill has historically been low and consequently we haven't been reliant on UKRI funding to fund TAs. We do not anticipate that the loss of funding will result in us no longer being able to support TAs after 2024. However, we are conscious that TA costs can be unpredictable and with our publishing outputs growing, rising VAT and wider pressures on university budgets, the situation could easily change. We are interested in rights retention (RR) as an alternative and complementary route to compliance and have begun exploratory discussions about what a RR policy might look like at Edge Hill. These discussions are in the very early stages and we are watching and learning from other institutions that are further ahead in this respect. We believe RR could form an important part of the sector's strategy to move away from its dependency on TAs in the future.

Requirement four: transparency

Q1. How did/would access to this type of cost transparency information affect your institution's decision making when considering joining TAs?

Answer:

It is particularly concerning that certain publishers are still withholding crucial information around cost transparency. The focus of the last five years has been on securing agreements that reduce and constrain costs and enable UK research to be published OA via a compliant route. Whilst it's fair to say that these two core objectives have largely been achieved, it feels as though far less progress has been made around the issue of cost transparency. On the one hand publishers will publicly and visibly state their support for open research, yet they continue to withhold information that is critical to understanding and evaluating the long-term cost implications and the sustainability of their agreements. Not sharing such data makes it impossible to understand if costs are reasonable and fair and commensurate with the services provided. A reluctance to share information also creates the impression that there is something to hide, which damages trust.

Up until now the lack of this information has not prevented us from joining TAs because meeting the primary objectives has been our priority as an institution and it feels like we have had to concede some things to achieve the other more immediate and important goals of reducing costs and increasing the amount of research published OA. However, as we start to look beyond the TA and consider the shape of future OA agreements, we believe that having greater cost transparency will be critical and this may become more of a deciding factor in our future evaluation of TAs. By not providing or obscuring cost transparency information, this enables publishers to act in ways that primarily serve their commercial interests, which is at odds with the sector's long-term goal to move to an open research landscape that is fairer and more equitable.

Q2. What else would give your institution confidence that publishers are splitting out different revenue components and aren't double-charging for the same services – eg, levying publishing charges (APCs) for publications in hybrid journals while not providing a proportionate decrease in subscription costs?

Answer:

Publishers committing to providing data on individual journal titles that show how their revenue is calculated and demonstrate a reduction in subscription costs as publishing increases [within the term of the TA]. Data that shows how revenue is reinvested into open access publishing and services.

Requirement five: efficiencies

Q1. To what extent have TAs delivered efficiencies at your institution when compared to managing OA payments outside an agreement? Please explain your answer and highlight any workflow areas requiring further improvements that would increase efficiencies.

Answer:

Our Research Office administers payments for APCs on a case-by-case basis. The process is for the researcher to supply an application form with the key information and making their request. Since the advent of TAs, applications will first go to the Head of Research Support Services in the library, to ensure the researcher is aware of the options presented through our TAs.

TAs have delivered efficiencies quite simply by reducing the number of cases we receive. This is less admin for us, and for the researchers too, who need not make a request in many cases. We could increase efficiencies further by having a single Jisc dashboard to administer (rather than one managed by each individual publisher) and the Transitional Agreement Look-Up tool [[Journal Checker Tool](#)] could be improved for us by allowing us to customise it and add in extra deals we hold (eg, the PLOS one).

One example of a publisher workflow area that could require improvement is with Taylor & Francis. We have supported an author who when publishing an article open access through the read and publish deal, had to provide an APC quote amount and quote number for the

article, even though no APC was to be paid. This was somewhat worrying and seemed completely unnecessary. Such an administrative burden for the author too. We are aware that other institutions are grappling with this too. For example, see excerpt from the Taylor & Francis deal guide provided by University of Reading.

“The author should click on the ‘request quote’ button and then fill in the affiliation details. The system will then alert the author that they are affiliated with an organisation that is part of the read and publish deal and invite them to request funding. A summary page will be displayed and the discount rate should be entered by default at 100%. The author should accept the quote at this stage and make a note of the quote number.”

<https://libguides.reading.ac.uk/open-access/apc-discounts>

Finally, although this question is focused on workflow efficiencies for authors and administrators, it is worth noting that there is still a great deal of inefficiency around managing VAT payments for the publish element, particularly for publishers like Taylor & Francis where the publish fee is not fixed each year. Budgeting for and managing these payments with our finance department is not straightforward and we would welcome further improvements to this process.

Q2. Does your institution have any concerns about the reduction/removal of friction in the author workflow within TAs?

Answer:

We have no concerns in principle, this is welcome. However, the additional requirements on the publisher to remove friction should not be a barrier to entry for smaller publishers entering into TAs with Jisc. Perhaps an exception could be made for smaller publishers for the first three years, etc.

Additionally, we are concerned that less friction and administrative burden could mean fewer checks in the process and result in us being levied with invoices that we are not set up to pay. For instance, we recently had an issue with publication fees for an article in the Hindawi journal Health & Social Care in the Community. The author decided to submit a paper in mid-2022 when the journal was a Wiley title and in our read and publish deal. By August she had submitted, and the journal had moved to being hosted by Hindawi (so fell out of the deal). We asked about the APC at this point, and Hindawi advised that the information would be available in January 2023. In January, the paper was accepted and even though by that point the Hindawi journals had moved back into the Wiley read and publish deal, we still received an APC invoice because of the submission date. We complained that a journal dropping in and out of chargeable periods and not providing financial information was unfair and not transparent, noting that we had been subscribed to the Wiley/Jisc OA agreement throughout this entire period. Our Wiley contact managed to resolve the issue eventually, but it created a lot of work for our Head of Research Support Services and the poor author (an early career researcher) was really stressed and upset.

Endnotes

1 **DOAJ Change Log**

2 Priem (2021)

3 ISSN, ISSN Portal and ROAD (2023)

4 Journal Checker Tool (no date b)

5 DOAJ (no date b)

6 API queries were made at different time points as 2022 transitional agreements were included, resulting in wider coverage of titles and inclusion of articles published in all titles in 2022.

7 Dimensions is an inter-linked research information system provided by **Digital Science**. Due to licensing and copyright restrictions, please ensure the appropriate acknowledgement of the use of Dimensions data is used, where the content of this report is reproduced.

8 ESAC (2023a)

9 Petrou (2021)

10 Norwegian Register for Scientific Journals, Series and Publishers (no date)

11 DOAJ (no date c)

12 CWTS Journal Indicators (no date)

13 Council of Australian University Librarians (Australia); Universitätsbibliothek - Clearingstelle für Konsortien (Austria); Canadian Research Knowledge Network (Canada); Consortia S.A.S. (Colombia); Royal Danish Library (Denmark); FinELib (Finland); Bielefeld University (Germany); Max Plank Digital Library (Germany); Maynooth University (Ireland); Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane (Italy); Universiteitsbibliotheken en Nationale Bibliotheek (Netherlands); FCCN (Portugal); Sikt – Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Norway); Qatar National Library (Qatar); King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (Saudi Arabia); South African National Library and Information Consortium (South Africa); Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain); Crue Universidades Españolas (Spain); National Library of Sweden (Sweden); Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries (Switzerland); and California Digital Library (United States of America)

14 Note that for Optica, the pre-TA subscription and publish fees were not sourced from LSM (where they were missing), but an internal report instead.

15 XE (2023)

16 Office for National Statistics (2023)

17 Office for National Statistics (2023)

18 Office for National Statistics (2023)

19 Office for National Statistics (2023)

20 EBSCO (2019), EBSCO (2020), EBSCO (2021), EBSCO (2022), EBSCO (2023)

21 Delta Think (2023)

22 RSNA, RIA, and T&F

23 CSHLP, Optica, and BUP

24 For more background on offsetting as a measure of financial transition to OA, refer to: Marques and Stone (2020)
Olsson et al. (2018)

25 AIP, Elsevier and Springer Nature

- 26 BUP, CUP, John Benjamins, NAS, T&F and Wolters Kluwer
- 27 RIA
- 28 All publishers except for: AIP, Bioscientifica, BUP, Elsevier, Future Science, IOP, IWAP, Rockefeller, Sage, Springer Nature, De Gruyter and Wiley.
- 29 UKRI (2020)
- 30 AIP, Elsevier and Springer Nature
- 31 See Jisc repository for [survey questions](#)
- 32 See Jisc repository for [case study template](#)
- 33 Association for Computing Machinery (2023a)
- 34 Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press (no date)
- 35 Shull (2021)
- 36 IOP Science (no date)
- 37 Biochemical Society and Portland Press (2019)
- 38 Royal Society (2023b)
- 39 Royal Society of Chemistry (2022)
- 40 Taylor & Francis (no date)
- 41 The Company of Biologists (no date)
- 42 Simmons and Strachan (2023)
- 43 Institutions were asked to review the following sources:
ACM slides
[PLOS Price Transparency Update 2021](#) blog post:
Submissions to the Journal Comparison Service, including Wiley

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- 109 **Figure 40:** list of publishers with unknown pre-TA APC expenditure and imputed estimates.

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